

How Could we Scale up the Qualification of Researchers for Trusted Research Environments

Preparing the Usership for the European Data Spaces

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Abstract

According to the Five Safes framework [UK Data Service], the ways in which research data are accessed should reflect their sensitivity. For less-sensitive research data, 'safe use' can be achieved when data are downloaded from online platforms, whereas more sensitive data may require the use of Secure Processing Environments (SPEs) or Trusted Research Environments (TREs). This diversity of data access routes can be seen across the National Research Data Infrastructure in Germany (NFDI) Consortia. Regardless of the access route, those working with research data should be 'safe people', who have been trained in the skills and knowledge to handle it safely. There is however little consistency in how, and to what standards, researchers have been trained.

To address this inconsistency, DAta LIteracy Alliance (DALIA) offers a comprehensive and standardised framework for those developing data access and literacy training, enabling users to locate high-quality training through a curated platform, that will provide them a clear and structured path to develop their data skills and obtain certifiable data literacy. This will facilitate seamless access to multiple data platforms and environments and thereby support, for example, cross-NFDI research projects.

While several training portals like Twillo and OERSI offer open educational resources, not many of them include tailored trajectories that a) build upon the users' current knowledge, b) reach a certifiable level of data literacy, and c) create a cross acceptance of those certificates in order to prevent multiple cumbersome qualification certifications for different portals.

As a use-case and an example of how training initiatives can be aligned with, and included in, the DALIA portal, the ASSURED project was identified. The project is developing a training and accreditation scheme for researchers and professionals across Germany who are accessing or handling highly sensitive data. This is highly relevant in the context of the EHDS (European Health Data Space), under which those working with data must be trained. ASSURED will help build knowledge through an online micro-learning approach, thereby offering trainees the opportunity to obtain a widely-recognised certification.

In this presentation, we will demonstrate how training initiatives such as ASSURED can be incorporated into DALIA, as well as show developments in improving the DALIA search portal to meet the needs and requirements of the user community.

Keywords: Use Case, User Story, Data Literacy, Search Platform, RDM Training

Resources

DALIA Search Platform. <https://search.dalia.education/basic> "Search platform for OER regarding data literacy"

Author contributions

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Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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